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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DILUTED FENTANYL, KETAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE AND PRIMING DOSE OF FENTANYL CITRATE ON CESSATION OF FENTANYL INDUCED COUGH (FIC)

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ABSTRACT

Fentanyl is commonly used as a preinduction adjunct to general anaesthesia. Incidence of fentanyl induced cough varies between 18-65%. Aims of the study are to evaluate the occurrence rate and severity of fentanyl induced cough and comparison of effectiveness of ketamine (0.5 mg/kg), priming dose of Fentanyl (0.5 µg/kg) one min before bolus of Fentanyl and diluted Fentanyl (10 cc with saline) to suppress fentanyl induced cough. 400 patients posted for elective surgeries under general anaesthesia were randomly allocated into 4 groups of 100 patients. During induction, Group S received saline and Group PK received Inj. Ketamine Hydrochloride (0.5 mg/kg) one minute before Inj. Fentanyl 2 µg/kg. Group PF received Inj. Fentanyl Citrate (0.5 µg/kg) one minute before Inj. Fentanyl 1.5 µg/kg. Group DF received Inj. Fentanyl 2 µg/kg diluted in saline upto 10 cc over 30 sec. Observation was done for occurrence and severity of cough for three minutes and heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure at 1 min before and 5 min after giving bolus of fentanyl. Incidence of fentanyl induced cough is significantly lower in Group DF (2%) as compared to others (45% in Group S, 10% in Group PK, 14% in Group PF). ($p < 0.0001$) Severity grade was mild (1-2 episode) in Group DF as compared to others. ($p < 0.0001$) Dilution of fentanyl (10 µg/ml) with normal saline and prolonged injection time is the simple and cost effective method to prevent fentanyl induced cough.

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INTRODUCTION

Opioids have been used to relieve anxiety and decrease pain associated with surgery.^[1] Fentanyl is commonly used as a preinduction adjunct to general anaesthesia because of its quick onset, short duration of action, intense analgesia, cardiovascular stability and low histamine release. However, intravenous administration of fentanyl during induction of general anaesthesia can also lead to some adverse events such as hypotension, bradycardia, respiratory depression, cyanosis, nausea, anaphylactoid reactions, cough, muscle rigidity, dizziness and confusion.^[2] Incidence of fentanyl induced cough varies between 18-65%.^[1] It is usually transient and self limiting in nature. It is necessary to prevent fentanyl induced cough in patients with some coexisting diseases like increased intracranial pressure, open eye injury, dissecting aortic aneurysm, pneumothorax or reactive airway diseases.^[3] Cough is the result of mechanical or chemical stimulation of sensory receptors within the respiratory tract. The afferent impulses from these receptors activate a putative brainstem centre.^[4] A pulmonary chemoreflex mediated by C-fibre receptors (also known as Juxtacapillary 'J' receptors) is thought to underlie this phenomenon. Opioid receptors have been shown in smooth muscles of trachea, bronchi and in alveolar walls but not in small airways. Alveolar wall opioid receptors may be associated with J receptors.^[5] Several pharmacological measures have been studied in an attempt to reduce this adverse effect with different rates of success like Inj. Morphine 0.2mg/kg IM^[6], Inj. Ketamine 0.5 mg/kg IV^[3], inhalation of terbutaline^[7], aerosol inhalation of salbutamol, beclomethasone or sodium chromoglycate^[8], Inj. Dexmedetomidine 0.5 µg/kg IV^[9], pre emptive Inj. Fentanyl 0.5 mg/kg^[10] and diluted injection of fentanyl with saline¹ and Inj. Dexamethasone (10 mg)^[11]. Aims of our study are to evaluate the occurrence of rate and severity of fentanyl induced cough and comparison of effectiveness of ketamine hydrochloride (0.5 mg/kg), priming dose of Fentanyl citrate (0.5 µg/kg) one minute before bolus dose of Fentanyl and diluted Fentanyl (10 cc with saline) to suppress fentanyl induced cough.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

Approval was obtained from ethical committee of the institute. Written and informed consent was taken from each patient. Four hundred patients aged between 18 and 65 years, of either sex, American society of anaesthesiologists' class I or II, weighing between 40-80 kg and scheduled for elective surgery under general anaesthesia were enrolled in the study. Exclusion criteria included history of asthma, chronic cough, smoking, upper respiratory tract infection in previous two weeks, impaired kidney or liver function, ongoing medications containing ACE inhibitors, anti depressant, broncho-dilators and steroids. All patients were premedicated with Tab. Lorazepam 0.5 mg at night before surgery. Four hundred patients were randomly divided into four groups by chit method. In operation theatre, venous access was established with 18 gauge cannula on the dorsum of the non-dominant hand. Intravenous ringer lactate started at a rate of 10 ml/kg/hour. Monitors attached were electrocardiography, non invasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry and capnography throughout the procedure. Study drugs were made by another anaesthetist who was not involved in the study. A stopwatch was used to calculate the injection time of each drug and interval time between injections. Preoxygenation was done for 5 minute with 100% oxygen at 6 litre/min. Inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.004 mg/kg and Inj. Ondansetron 0.1 mg/kg IV given. In group S, saline 2 cc was given over 5 seconds. In group PK, Inj. Ketamine hydrochloride 0.5 mg/kg was given diluted in 2 cc over 5 seconds. In both group S and PK, Inj. Fentanyl citrate 2 µg/kg was given IV over 5 seconds after a waiting period of one minute. In group PF, priming dose of Inj. Fentanyl citrate (0.5 µg/kg) diluted in 2 cc over 5 seconds. After waiting period of one minute, bolus dose of Inj. Fentanyl citrate 1.5 µg/kg given over 5 seconds. In group DF, Inj. Fentanyl citrate 2 µg/kg diluted upto 10 cc with saline 0.9% given over 30 seconds. Heart rate, systolic BP and diastolic BP at 1 min before and 5 min after giving Inj. Fentanyl citrate bolus were noted for comparison. An observer, unaware of type of medications given to the patients, recorded the occurrence and severity of coughing for 3 minute duration. Severity of cough was graded as none (0 episode), mild (1-2 episodes), moderate (3-4 episodes) and severe (≥5 episodes). Primary end point of the study is occurrence of Fentanyl induced cough. Other adverse events associated with fentanyl and ketamine such as apnoea, truncal rigidity, nausea, hypotension, respiratory depression, bradycardia or altered consciousness were also noted before induction of anaesthesia. Secondary end point of the study is occurrence of other events as described above. Standard induction of general anaesthesia with Inj. Thiopentone sodium 7 mg/kg and Inj. Succinylcholine 2 mg/kg was done. Bag and mask ventilation was done with 100% oxygen for 30 seconds. All patients were intubated with proper sized cuffed endotracheal tube. Tube position was confirmed after checking bilateral equal air entry and then tube was fixed. Anaesthesia was maintained with 50% O₂ + 50% N₂O + Isoflurane with controlled ventilation using circle absorbent circuit. Inj. Vecuronium Bromide (0.08mg/kg) IV was used as non-depolarizing muscle relaxant. After completion of surgery, neuromuscular blockade was reversed with Inj. Glycopyrrolate (0.008mg/kg) and Inj. Neostigmine (0.05mg/kg) IV. Extubation was done after adequate oropharyngeal and endotracheal suctioning. Patient was shifted to post operative ward. Statistical Analysis:

Considering the expected incidence of cough following peripherally administered intravenous fentanyl to be 20% and power of 80%, the minimum sample size required in each group was 96. Anticipating some variability in reduction, we enrolled 100 patients in each group. Patients' characteristics were compared using one-way ANOVA. Comparison between the groups was performed for overall incidence of cough and severity of cough by Chi-squared test. Statistical analysis was done using graphpad.com. A P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 400 patients were included in the study. There were no significant difference in demographic data between the four groups including age, sex and weight (p>0.05 Table 1). Different surgeries performed on the patients were also not significantly different (p>0.05 Graph 1). Incidence of cough was significantly lower in group DF as compared to others (p <0.0001 Table 2). Severity of cough varies between the groups showing significantly decreased with group PF and group DF (p <0.0001 Table 2). There was significant delayed onset of cough with diluted fentanyl (10 µg/ml) with prolonged injection time (30 sec) (p <0.0001 Table 2).

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA:

	GROUP S (n=100)	GROUP PK (n=100)	GROUP PF (n=100)	GROUP DF (n=100)	p value*
AGE; year	48.73±11.75	49.21±10.11	47.49±11.81	46.6±11.74	0.35
SEX: F/M	49/51	47/53	49/51	48/52	0.99
WEIGHT; kg	53.69±7.25	53.3±6.21	52.49±7.71	51.6±6.14	0.14

Data presented as mean ± SD or number. Age, sex and weight were similar in all the groups (*p>0.05). Various types of surgeries for which patients were operated are shown graphically below.

GRAPH 1: TYPE OF SURGERY:

TABLE 2: INCIDENCE AND SEVERITY OF COUGH:

	GROUP S	GROUP PK	GROUP PF	GROUP DF	p value†
Cough incidence	45	10	14	2	<0.0001
SEVERITY: None	55	90	86	98	<0.0001
Mild	20	9	8	2	
Moderate	24	1	6	0	
Severe	1	0	0	0	
Time of onset (sec)	21.5±3.28	31.2±3.45	33.14±4.06	36.5±2.12	<0.0001

Data presented as number or mean ± SD. †P <0.05 is considered significant.

Table 2 shows comparison of incidence of cough, severity of cough and time of onset of cough in all groups. Incidence of cough was lowest in Group DF as compared to all other groups (p <0.0001). Group PK and Group DF had lower incidence of cough as compared with Group S (p <0.05).

Graph 2 shows comparison of severity of cough among the different groups. There was significantly less incidence of moderate and severe cough in group DF and group PF as compared to group S and group PK (p 0.0001).

GRAPH 2: SEVERITY OF COUGH:

TABLE 3: INTERGROUP ANALYSIS OF INCIDENCE OF COUGH:

Intergroup Analysis			p value*
Incidence of cough	Group S	Group DF	<0.0001
	Group PK	Group PF	0.5
	Group PK	Group DF	0.03
	Group PF	Group DF	0.002

*p <0.05 is considered significant.

Incidence of cough is not significantly different between group PK and group PF (p = 0.5). It indicates that both measures are equally effective to control FIC. However, Group DF has significantly lower incidence of FIC as compared to Group PK (p 0.03) and Group PF (p 0.002).

GRAPH 3: TIME OF ONSET OF COUGH:

Graph shows delayed onset of FIC in Group DF as compared to other groups.

TABLE 4: INTERGROUP ANALYSIS OF TIME OF ONSET OF COUGH:

Intergroup Analysis			p value [§]
TIME OF ONSET	Group S	Group DF	<0.0001
	Group PK	Group PF	<0.0001
	Group PK	Group DF	<0.0001
	Group PF	Group DF	<0.0001

[§]P <0.05 is considered significant.

Table 4 shows that there is delayed onset of cough that is statistically significant in group DF as compared to Group S, Group PK and Group PF (p <0.0001). In intergroup analysis, Group PF shows significantly delayed onset of cough as compared to group PK (p <0.0001).

TABLE 5: HEART RATE COMPARISON:

	HEART RATE(beats/min)		p value
	1 min before	5 min after	
Group S	83.25±9.79	80.24±7.60	0.02
Group PK	84.18±10.06	87.21±10.36	0.03
Group PF	80.28±9.35	82.16±9.15	0.15
Group DF	84.22±10.35	86.22±10.09	0.16

Data shown as mean ± sd. ^{||}p <0.05 is considered significant.

Table shows significant difference of heart rate 1 min before and 5 min after giving bolus fentanyl in Group S (p 0.02) and Group PK (p 0.03). There is no significant difference of heart rate I Group PF and Group DF.

TABLE 6: COMPARISON OF SYSTOLIC AND DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE:

	Systolic Blood pressure (mm Hg)			Diastolic Blood pressure (mm Hg)		
	1 min before	5 min after	p value [†]	1 min before	5 min after	p value ^{**}
Group S	133.07± 11.67	131.43± 7.24	0.23	82.42± 8.02	80.68± 8.09	0.12
Group PK	134.47± 11.29	136.25± 8.99	0.21	84.24± 9.22	86.5± 7.96	0.06
Group PF	125.67± 12.02	123.05± 8.81	0.08	88.06± 9.11	86.02± 7.97	0.09
Group DF	136.1± 10.99	134.55± 10.11	0.3	88.62± 9.46	90.02± 8.26	0.2

Data shown as mean ± sd. [†]*** p <0.05 is significant.

Table 6 shows comparison of systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure 1 min before and 5 min after giving fentanyl bolus. No significant change was seen in SBP and DBP in any of groups.

DISCUSSION

In our study, we observed that ketamine (0.5 mg/kg) as well as priming dose of fentanyl (0.5 µg/kg) equally decreases the incidence of FIC (10% and 14% respectively). But, diluted fentanyl (10 µg/ml) with prolong injection time (30 sec) almost eliminated the FIC with only 2% cough incidence.

Pressor response to laryngoscopy and intubation is associated with sympatho adrenal responses like hypertension, tachycardia due to increased plasma catecholamine concentrations. These changes are well tolerated by healthy individuals. But in patients with hypertension, heart disease and coronary artery disease, open eye injury, neurosurgical procedure^[12]; the pressure response can result in the complications.

Many studies have been done using different dose of fentanyl and by different routes of administration of fentanyl with the incidence of fentanyl induced cough between 18% and 65%. The severity and time of onset also remains different. In the study by Lin et al.^[13], 65% of the patients coughed following 2.5 µg/kg fentanyl through a peripheral venous line within 2 seconds. A 46% incidence of cough has been reported with 7 µg/kg fentanyl administered through a central venous catheter administered over 1 sec by Bohrer et al.^[14]. Another study by Lui et al.^[7], showed that 43% of patients coughed after receiving 5 µg/kg fentanyl injected through a peripheral venous line over 5 s. Pandey et al.^[15] reported that 35% of patients coughed following 3 µg/kg fentanyl given intravenously through a peripheral venous line. This studies mentioned that high dose of fentanyl can lead to higher incidence of reflex cough. Phua et al.^[6] found that fentanyl 1.5 µg/kg when administered via a peripheral venous line elicited a cough in 28% of the patients and a similar incidence of cough was observed by Agarwal et al.^[8] following 2 µg/kg fentanyl given intravenously through the peripheral route over a period of 5 seconds. In a more recent study by Lin et al.^[16], 18% of patients coughed after receiving 100 or 150 µg fentanyl (this was not based on the body weight of patients) via a peripheral intravenous line. Our study has shown that undiluted fentanyl 2 µg/kg, when administered through a peripheral venous line, provokes coughing in 45% of patients. This discrepancy can be explained by differences in injection dose and time. In terms of the results of previous studies, fentanyl induced cough seems to be a dose-dependent effect^[1]. Therefore, in the present study, we chose a medium dose of fentanyl (2µg/kg), a dose which is commonly used in daily practice.

Pretreatment with ketamine 0.5 mg/kg is associated with attenuating the FIC (0/100; P = 0.001) compared with the placebo group (23/100).^[3] This result is quiet similar with that of our study with same dose of ketamine (10% FIC). The presence of NMDA receptors has been reported in the larynx, lung, and airways, and activation of these receptors can trigger airway constriction.^[17] Therefore, the direct bronchodilation effect of ketamine may be attributed to its NMDA-receptor antagonism as well as through a mechanism independent of NMDA receptors thus eliminating fentanyl induced cough.^[18] Kamei reported that N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonists are capable of modulating the cough reflex.^[19]

Yeh et al.^[20] observed the frequency of cough in the ketamine pretreatment (0.15mg/kg) group (7.2%) with observation time of one second after giving Inj. Fentanyl 1.5 µg/kg. In our study, Inj. Ketamine hydrochloride (0.5 mg/kg), used as priming dose, resulted in 10% cough incidence. This variation may be due to difference of the dose of fentanyl (1.5 vs 2 µg/kg) and also due to difference of the time of observation (1 min vs 3 min) between the two studies.

On deriving the minimum dose required to produce FIC, Cheng Yong Gu et al.^[10] speculate that small priming doses of fentanyl (0.5 µg/kg) may result in depletion of neurotransmitters in peripheral nerve fibers. Neurotransmitters released by pre-emptive injections of small doses of fentanyl may not reach threshold levels, hence resulting in no fentanyl induced cough due to exhaustion of neurotransmitters. Incidence of FIC is almost similar with high pre-emptive (1.5 µg/kg) fentanyl and bolus 2.5 µg/kg (no pre-emptive dose) 64% v/s 68% incidence respectively. So, they concluded that the dose of fentanyl that induces cough may be between 1.0 and 1.5 µg/kg based on the finding of the study.

Another study by Bo-Xiang Du et al.^[21] showed that a priming fentanyl dose 0.5 µg/kg decreased the incidence and severity of FIC and a priming fentanyl dose of 1.0 µg/kg or 1.5µg/kg had no effect on FIC. This result is consistent with our study showing only 14% incidence of FIC with priming dose fentanyl 0.5 µg/kg (group PF).

H Yu et al.^[1] concluded that dilution of fentanyl to 10 µg/ml with 0.9% saline combined with a prolonged injection time (30 sec) eliminates fentanyl-induced cough. Our study also showed lowest incidence in group DF (10 µg/ml over 30 sec, 2%) FIC. The exact mechanism by which dilution of fentanyl reduces the incidence of cough is not known. The osmolality and pH (especially produced by citrate in fentanyl citrate solution) of fentanyl solution were changed due to dilution with 0.9% saline so that diminished stimulation to irritant receptors in tracheal smooth muscle and C fibre receptors in pulmonary vessels was achieved, preventing the cough reflex.

The 68% incidence of cough, in the absence of pre-emptive fentanyl, was attributed to higher incidence to a faster rate of bolus injection of fentanyl (bolus time: 2 s).^[9] Therefore, fentanyl should not be injected with such rapidity in clinical practice. Fentanyl-induced cough was minimized simply by slowing the rate of injection without any drug pretreatment.^[16] From the pharmacokinetic point of view, the duration of drug injection may affect the peak plasma concentration, with a longer injection time resulting in a smaller peak concentration

L Bailey et al.^[5] suggested that the elicitation of the cough reflex following opioid administration seems to be temporally related to the circulation time and may serve as a clinical clue to 'vein-to-brain' time, or cardiac output. From the pharmacokinetic point of view, the duration of drug injection may affect the peak plasma concentration, with a longer injection time resulting in a smaller peak concentration. The threshold for fentanyl-induced cough may be reached more easily at a large bolus dose and a larger peak plasma concentration. The longer the injection time, the less frequent is fentanyl-induced cough. A specific receptor, known as the rapidly adapting receptor, is thought to be the cough receptor. We also found that slowing the rate of injection reduced not only the incidence but also lessened the severity of cough (Table 2). From our study, we can say that if bolus fentanyl (2 µg/kg) is diluted and injected slowly, the incidence of cough reduces drastically to only 2%.

Studies^[22,23] mentioned that slow (over 10 sec rather than 2 sec or 6 sec) injection of fentanyl citrate definitely reduces both the incidence and severity of fentanyl induced cough by a simple, inexpensive, effective and very cost effective way of solving the issue of fentanyl induced cough. However, we adopted the injection time of 5 s in Groups S, PK and PF. But we found the injection of the volume of diluted fentanyl solution (10 CC) could not be achieved within 5 seconds. Interestingly, in our study we found that the both incidence and severity of cough could even be effectively reduced by the dilution of fentanyl to 10µg/ml with 0.9% saline with prolonged injection time of 30 seconds.

Hemodynamic parameters as baseline and one min after giving fentanyl bolus of 1.5 µg/kg showed no significant difference.^[3] In our study, hemodynamic parameters at one min before and 5 min after giving fentanyl bolus, there is significant increase in heart rate in group PK (Table 5, P = 0.03) with no change in systolic and diastolic blood pressure. In group DF, there is no significant change in hemodynamic parameters.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that fentanyl induced cough should be prevented for smooth induction of general anaesthesia. Dilution of fentanyl (10µg/ml with 0.9% normal saline) with prolonged injection time (30 sec) can effectively reduce the incidence and severity of fentanyl induced cough. Whereas, priming dose of ketamine (0.5 mg/kg) can be an alternate way to reduce the incidence of fentanyl induced cough.

ABBREVIATIONS

FIC Fentanyl Induced Cough

Conflict of interests:

All authors have no conflicts of interests.

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